

INVESTIGATING CONSUMER RESPONSIVENESS TO MOBILE MARKETING IN JOHANNESBURG

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Abstract

Traditional communication mix elements have become pricey. Therefore there is a growing need for marketers to find cheaper alternatives to communicate with their target audience. Mobile phone marketing will lower the costs of advertising and at the same time improve relationships between marketers and consumers as it targets the personal element of marketing communication. According to research, 29 million people use mobile phones in South Africa. The research objectives seek to determine the different uses of mobile technology by consumers, how mobile phone users interact with mobile marketing techniques, and to make recommendations on the optimal use of mobile marketing. This quantitative study established that, although it might not be the first choice of receiving marketing communications, the majority of the people would still like to receive adverts via their mobile, proving that mobile marketing has a place in marketing. The findings revealed that 34% of South African mobile phone users have smartphones, this creates a new market for mobile internet, social media, and mobile email adverts. It is important that marketers should also use other methods of marketing communication mix as 28 million people use radio and 26 million people use televisions in South Africa, proving that these gadgets are still important in the consumers' lives and in information sharing. Mobile marketing cannot replace the conventional marketing communication methods completely but can complement the efforts and create an interactive platform for marketers and their consumers.

Keywords: mobile marketing; communication methods; mobile adverts.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mobile phones have enhanced communication in the world as progressively more people are using this technology. It is believed that on average a person will check their messages every 15 minutes and companies are now able to increase profitability and productivity by using mobile technology. Access to mobile phones is increasing in most developing countries, with many people now having access to mobile phones than have to a bank account, to electricity, or even to clean water. It is currently the most affordable means of communicating with customers if

compared to the traditional communication mix elements. Early adopters have been able to reduce their marketing spend whilst still getting the highest advertising value. The results of this study will guide marketers on the correct usage of mobile marketing. Most communication mix elements tend to be costly. Therefore the use of mobile phone marketing will lower the costs of advertising and at the same time improve the relationship between the marketer and the consumers as it targets the personal element of marketing communication. Numerous companies have started to include mobile marketing in their integrated communication mix.

1.2 Background to the study

Kotler and Keller (2006:6) outline that the American Marketing Association sees marketing as a skill of selecting target markets and creating value for customers. Marketers are in a dilemma on how to reach young consumers. This group has become time conscious, but they, however, spend most of their time using the latest technology and gadgets. The young consumers enjoy communicating using this technology. Mobile phones have rapidly become pivotal to technology conversion. As the abilities have extended, a significant increase in the importance of young consumers segment has been seen. Mobile phones have become the gadget of choice among young consumers. "Mobile technology is the most ubiquitous technology, with nearly seven billion mobile worldwide subscriptions recorded in 2012, implying 75 percent of the world's population had access to mobile technology" (GSMA Intelligence, 2014). Whilst in search of a means to link technology and marketing communication, the evolution of the mobile industry and mobile technology has been identified as the newest medium in the marketing industry. Mobile phones are slowly becoming the most highly used electronic gadget and are used across all demographics. John Hutton, the telecoms director of Nielsen South Africa, in his report entitled 'Mobile dominates South Africa', supports the above observation when he states that in 2010, 29 million South Africans used mobile phones. An In-Mobi independent Ad Network revealed that it is imperative for companies to look at Mobile Marketing strategies that are innovative in order to obtain full benefits from mobile marketing. The year 2013 recorded increases in revenue from the sales of Smartphones and Tablets. The competition of gadgets has increased with the rollout of Windows 8 and the RIMs platform.

1.3 Problem statement

The evolution of mobile technology and its advancement has created a platform for marketers to communicate with current and potential consumers. This form of communication is instant as it offers opportunities to interact with recipients. Over the years we have seen banks moving to cellphone banking, developing mobile phone applications and creating platforms for interaction with consumers. It is in this context that there is need to explore the effectiveness of mobile marketing. Recommendations will be made to advertisers in order to assist them in the correct application of mobile marketing elements, whilst also advising on how much emphasis should be given to mobile marketing.

1.4 Research questions

- What is the perception of consumers regarding mobile marketing techniques?
- To what extent are mobile phone users' decisions influenced by mobile marketing techniques?
- What recommendations can be given to marketers regarding acceptable mobile marketing?

1.5 Significance of the study

Numerous studies have been done on mobile phones and their general usage, but there have not been many studies that have focused on mobile marketing. This study will augment on existing knowledge concerning mobile marketing. It will assess the different elements of mobile phone usage and how they have been adopted into the communication mix. It will also explore consumer responsiveness to mobile phone marketing. Recommendations from this study will help marketers choose the correct mobile marketing element to include in their communication mix.

1.6 Conclusions

Mobile marketing is slowly been adopted as a cost-effective mode of communication. It has however not been used to its fullest potential. With many South Africans spending their time on their mobile phones, it is time for marketers to make use of mobile marketing elements.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Smartphones are becoming progressively more important in the world, According to a research done by Kerigan marketing in 2014, it can be seen that over one billion smartphones were shipped (sold) out in 2013 alone. The single function that defines a smartphone is the ability to browse the internet. This is one proof that Internet browsing on mobile phones and tablets or on the go as some would define it is growing. We cannot talk about mobile phones without including tablets, in Africa, the use of tablets as a mobile phone is increasing. The sales of tablets globally far exceeded that of desktop computers in 2012. In 2013 the sales of tablets surpassed those of desktop computers as well as notebooks. The sales of a device can be used as indicative of usage. When the first iPhone and iPad were released in 2007 and 2010 respectively, the sales for both desktop computers and notebooks dropped and have not been able to recover despite the introduction of newer models.

2.1 Uses of mobile phones

Although the primary use of a mobile phone is making calls, the new features of mobile phones have made them versatile and increased the uses causing making calls to become less important to users of mobile phones. The study conducted by Taxi app Hailo on the uses of mobile phones established that average people spend almost two hours a day using mobile phones. People spend most of their time sending messages, emails and also surfing the net. 40% of the mobile phone users in the study revealed that the call function on their phones was not important and if removed it won't be missed.

2.2 Global mobile internet traffic

In a study conducted by Kerrigan marketing in 2014, it was found that 25% of the traffic that browse the internet use mobile devices as the browsing tool. In Africa mobile internet traffic has grown by 20% between 2013 and 2014, the total mobile traffic is now 38% compared to the mobile traffic in 2013 which was at 18%. This is shown in the graph below which is an extract from the report. These results show that companies must become serious about using the internet as a form of marketing their products. If a business does not use mobile internet, they will be missing an opportunity to talk to 38% of the internet traffic in Africa. In a study conducted by Pew Research Center on Cellphones in Africa, it can be seen that 90% of the sample had cellphones in South Africa in the year 2014. Of the 90% who have cellphones, 34% had smartphones, this means 34% are able to use mobile phones to visit and browse the internet. In the African countries which were part of the research, South Africa has the most mobile phones and smartphones.

In the same study, results showed that of the 34% users in South Africa with smartphones, 41% are aged between 18- to 34-years and 27% are over 35 years. This means 14% are younger than 18 years. In Africa it can be seen in the above graph that the most used feature on the mobile phones is sending text messages, taking pictures and payment portals. The use of mobile banking in Africa is increasing year on year with banks introducing mobile apps, cellphone banking and mobile payment platforms such as Mpesa. Some other mobile phone most used functions are checking the news, social media and checking health information. Cellphone ownership in Africa has surged in a short space of time. Mobile forms have changed communication in Africa. As depicted in the graph above the cellphone ownership in South Africa grew from 33 % in 2001 to 89% in 2014.

2.3 South African mobile phone usage

South Africa is ranked the fifth in the world when ranked in terms of mobile data usage. In the research conducted by AC Nielsen in 2010, 11% of the respondents claimed they use their mobile phones to browse the internet whilst 85% said they use their mobile phones for Facebook access. 69% of the mobile phones consumers said they prefer to send messages because it is cheaper than calling. 60% of the mobile phone users in South Africa are aware of mobile phone banking facilities and only 21% use cellphone banking.

2.4 The consumer

A consumer is the main player in the marketplace, he is defined as the individual person or organisation which purchases or consumes available products and services. Conversely, there is a thin line between the shopper and the consumer. The Shopper is referred to as the person who concludes the purchase of any good or service, whilst the consumer is the person who uses the product or service. Shoppers can be individuals as in the case of a mother who purchases milk for her baby, she is not the one who will drink the milk but the baby. They can also be people acting on behalf of an organisation to conclude the purchase of a particular product or service. The consumer is the person or people who consume the purchased goods. Schiffman and Lazar Kanuk (2009:234) express consumer responsiveness as the ultimate test for marketing communication. The feedback received from consumers after receiving marketing communication. This feedback is usually in the form of action, which will either make consumers to buy the advertised product. Obtaining feedback is important in both interpersonal and mass communication. Jobber and Ellis-Chadwick. (2013:420) argue that communicators need to understand their target market before encoding messages otherwise the response will be disbelief and rejection. Consumer response in personal selling is instant, however in other marketing communication types it may rely on research to estimate reactions to the communication. There are differences in how consumers respond to services and products. The responsiveness was fairly low for all media, however, when the groups were divided, it was found that there were also some consumers that respond positively to communication. "The emergence of digital media has increased the number of ways to interact with consumers. The variation in the responsiveness to products and services for different media indicates that it is important to have an understanding of how the media adds and subtracts value." (Heinonen, K. Strandvik, T. & (2005:64

2.5 Mobile marketing elements

Marketing using mobile phones is defined as any form of marketing communication conveyed through a mobile phone. The aim is to offer possible opportunities for value creation for consumers (Anckar & D'Incau, 2000). Kotler and Keller 2009:57 states that mobile marketing is an opportunity for companies to reach customers on the move.

Mobile phones can be used to send and receive coupons, mobile ads, samples and important information. It offers a platform for interaction between customers and marketers. General Motors once used this platform when they launched a mobile marketing campaign on its Pontiac C. They asked consumers to take a photo of the sports sedan with their phone and send it to GM in return for a classic plunk rock ringtone, and they received 18500 photos mostly from their target market of young male under the age of 25 (Kotler and Keller 2009:57-58). One might ask where marketers get information of potential consumers. Kotler and Keller (2009:189) describe how wireless carriers have a variety of useful data of their customers, this data varies from demographic data, geographic data and content purchasing habits. The mobile technology is fast advancing and offering more and more options for marketers to use in their communication Mix, it has advanced from just offering Multimedia Messaging Service and Short Messaging Service to offering a wide range of options namely:

- Smartphone applications – more and more companies are creating applications for smartphones, these are software applications which are designed to run on a smartphone, for example, Discovery Health, FNB.
- USSD (Unstructured Supplementary Services: it is defined as techniques used by GSM cellular telephones to converse with the computers of service providers, examples are Prepaid Callbacks and Mobile Banking.
- Mobi sites: websites designed to run on cellphones, the main website redirects the user to a mobi site for example SAA
- QR (Barcode Scanning): this is a program which can be downloaded onto the mobile phones which enable them to scan a barcode and the information about a product, promotion or place are displayed on their phone. This barcoding system is also used for phone-to-phone communication.
- Mobile Shopping: Consumers use their mobile phones to go onto the internet and do shopping, some retailers; for example, Jenny Penny has launched mobile applications which facilitate easy access to their site for mobile users.
- Location Services: a good example is Google maps; this is the mobile phone version of navigation systems such as Garmin. These allow the consumer to easily locate places and even provide a map and direction using mobile data.
- Social networking, from email to social networking that is Twitter, WhatsApp, Blackberry services as examples.

2.6 Mobile marketing receptiveness

Kotler and Keller (2009:189) tell us the findings from the Harris interactive: “80% of respondents were open to receiving marketing messages on their mobile phones provided the adverts were targeted.” They found that young people between the ages of 15-19 are a very attractive market. In the UK, 99% of this age group have cellphones and are heavy spenders; \$202.9 million was spent on downloadable content, whilst text messages accounted for \$570 million in 2005. Some people are more receptive to mobile marketing than others, and in as much as blanket adverts are sent to consumers, not all consumers remember seeing adverts. In AC Nielsen’s Mobile insights 2011:28, 55% of the people interviewed remember seeing an advert on their mobile phones, the most common advert being a SMS advert. Although Virgin Mobile users seem to have a high recollection of mobile internet adverts, it is clear that the SMS medium is the one which most users connect with. Another area which is growing in South Africa is mobile banking; this can be in the form of cellphone banking, mobile internet, or a bank mobile application. This service is deemed to be fast, cheaper and highly effective. AC Nielsen Mobile Insights 2011:29 found that only 40% of the

interviewed mobile users are aware of mobile banking. FNB's e-wallet is the one which most users are aware. Andrews, Drennan and Russell-Bennett, (2012) found in a mobile experience analysis of three different profiles: Pragmatics, Connectors and Revellers. The Pragmatics only saw mobile phones value as a functional communication tool. The Connectors, similar to the Pragmatics, are described as also seeing the importance of social media on their phones whilst the Revellers are the ones who enjoy the mobile phones and are hooked by the different functionalities of the mobile phones. Pragmatics and Connectors are found to be receptive to some mobile marketing technics like SMS as long as they are specific to their area, home and work; these should be a limited number. They have more interest in entering promotions via SMS or even via a web form. They believe that there is enough marketing around them without being bombarded with marketing on their phones. On the other hand, the Revellers are described as the group which do not believe there is enough marketing around them.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Two research approaches, qualitative (Phenomenological) and quantitative (Positivist) are identified by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2007). Berg (2001) singularizes between the two approaches; qualitative and quantitative research, arguing that the qualitative research approach refers to the meanings, impressions, explanations, characteristics, representations, symbols and depiction of things, while the quantitative research approach denotes to the measures and counts of things. Qualitative research is used to learn more about a product or anything which cannot ordinarily be observed. The focus is on understanding consumer perceptible. This study will adopt the quantitative approach, an attempt to test the theory on mobile phone users' responsiveness to mobile marketing techniques. The research instruments which will aid the study are well-structured questionnaires.

3.1 Target population

The term used to describe the parting of the whole group (population) into small groups is called sampling. A single unit is called a population element. Measurement and observations are taken from an element. A population is the whole group of potential elements from which elements are taken. There two procedures which can be employed to select a sample, probability and non-probability sampling. The sample size for this study is 200. The target population is mobile phone users living in Randburg, (Randburg area includes: Ferndale, Blairgowrie, Boskruin, Olivedale, Northriding, Windsor, Cresta, Randpark Ridge, Jukskei Park, and Cosmo City), both male and female who own a mobile handset and use any of the available networks in South Africa. The focus will be on people aged between 20 years to 45 years.

- For the early 20's age group, we will go to universities namely Monash University
- For adults who aged between late 20's and older
 - Invite people from my workplace and some clients
 - Invite some people from church
 - Intercept shoppers at shopping malls, hair salons, and taxi ranks. These will be intercepted at random, ensuring the right mix of sex and age groups.

3.2 Data collection instruments

There are various instruments available for data collection. Saunders *et al.* (2007:103) assert that data collection can be done using six research instruments these are namely: Observations, interviews, documentation, questionnaires, archival records and standardized tests. Cooper and Schindler, (2007:13) define a research instrument as a reliable

and valid research measurement tool. For this study, the primary data collection method chosen is a questionnaire as it is regarded as an unbiased instrument used to collect data.

3.3 Validity and reliability

If one is planning a research or the interpretation of findings of other studies, an assessment of the impact of the results depends on the concepts of validity and reliability (Shuttleworth, 2008:1). In fact, the validity of a research study is the extent to which a study specifically answers the question(s) it was designed to meet. According to Shuttleworth (2008) the reliability of a research instrument relates to the extent to which repeated measures or assessments provide consistent results on the same initial conditions.

3.4 Pilot study

A pilot study is a miniature form of the main study. Saunders *et al.* (2007:386) observe that a pilot study enables the assessment of the questions' validity and the dependability of the collected data. In our pilot study, we tested the length of the questionnaire, clarity of instructions and questions, grammar, and layout. Cooper and Schindler (2006:77) suggest conducting a data analysis from the pilot study data. The reason is to make sure that the answers given meet the aim of the study. The distribution and collection method used is verified by the pilot study. The questionnaire was sent to ten respondents in order to assess its feasibility.

3.5 Data analysis

There are several interrelated procedures required for summarizing and rearranging data during the data analysis stage. For this study, the collected data will be captured and then grouped appropriately. The data will be captured in Microsoft Excel and will be analysed using SPSS version 21 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences).

3.5.1 Ethical considerations

The rules which distinguish between wrong and right are referred to as ethics; it can also refer to what is acceptable and what is not acceptable when conducting a research study (Shamoo & Resnik, 2009:420). Prior consent was obtained from participants by using a cover letter, which contains contacts details in case they wish to verify the legitimacy of the study. Confidentiality is key, all participants' information and completed questionnaires will not be shared with anyone. Questionnaires were destroyed after the study was completed. The identity of the participants will not be mentioned in any way, all the gathered information will be used for purposes of this study only and will be treated as confidential. Only respondents with the necessary legal capacity (adults) were asked to participate in the research.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

The total respondents who responded to this survey were 177; however, 18 respondents were not eligible as they fell outside of the defined target population (falling below the age of 20 years). The respondents were from all facets of life, from university level to retired people. 53% of the respondents were female and 47% were male. 42% of the total respondents were between 30 years and 39 years of age, 24% were 20-29 years old and 25% were older than 40 years. Of the respondents, 47% were managerial employees and business owners.

Figure 1: Location distribution

Most of the people who participated in the survey live in Blairgowrie and Ferndale, 25% live in Northriding, Olivedale and Boskruijn, 19% in Jukskei, 11% live in Randpark Ridge and Ferndale, 10% live in Cosmo and 7% live in Windsor and Cresta. The age groups are approximately normally distributed. Most of the participants are aged 30 – 39 years, 24% of the participants are aged 20 – 29 years, 16% are aged 40 – 49 years, 9% aged 40 – 49 years and 9% aged between 15 -19 Years. The 15 – 19-year-olds were not allowed to participate as they were below the targeted age. Most of the participants (53%) were female and 47% were male.

Figure 2: Occupations of participants

A large percentage of the participants (25%) are business owners, 22% are managerial employees and clerical staff, 18% are university or college students with less than 10% work in other occupations.

4.1 Results by question

When respondents were asked the mobile network used, Most of the participants use Vodacom as their mobile network, 25% use Cell C and MTN, and 21% use Telkom.

Figure 3: Internet usage

Most of the participants use the internet for work-related purposes, 19% use the internet for banking, 14% use the internet for emails, news & study and less than 10% of the participants use the internet for other reasons as shown in the graph above.

Figure 4: Preferred source for product information

A large percentage of the participants prefer email as the source for product information, 19% prefer the internet, 15% prefer the social media, 10% prefer Pinterest and less than 10% prefer YouTube, Instagram, and online games. All the participants said they have once received an advert on mobile phone.

Figure 5: Statistics on adverts received

25% of the participants said the advert they received was through MMS, 23% said it was through SMS, 19% said it was through a phone call, 11% said through Twitter, 10% said through Facebook, 5% said through WhatsApp and 7% said through all the platforms. Almost every participant can recall any advert he/she received on mobile phone.

Figure 6: Response to adverts

Most of the participants (30%) have responded to adverts concerning travel, accommodation and restaurants. 21% of the participants have responded to adverts concerning clothing, cosmetics, and jewellery. 16% have responded to adverts concerning cellphones, mobile networks, and electronics. 10% have responded to online specials and promotions. Another 10% of the participants have responded to adverts concerning cars, insurance and house. 5% have responded to detergents and 8% have not responded to an advert yet. Most of the participants (26%) remember the adverts because they are frequently sent, 24% remember them because they saved their money, 17% remember because they interested them, 15% still remember the adverts because they received them recently and 9% remember them because they were very graphic. 8% said they don't remember any advert. Most of the participants said they have responded to a mobile phone advert. 9% have not yet responded to a mobile phone advert. Most of the participants (32%) who responded to mobile adverts responded to car, insurance and house adverts. 27% responded to cellphones, mobile networks, and electronics adverts. 22% responded to clothing, cosmetics, and jewellery adverts. Less than 10% responded to other product adverts. 51% of the participants have purchased the product that was advertised to them on mobile phone. 49% of the participants did not purchase the product that was advertised to them on mobile phone. Most of the participants (66%) would like to receive adverts via mobile phone and 34% of the participants do not like to receive adverts via mobile phone. Most of the participants (49%) prefer mobile adverts on online specials and promotions, 24% prefer mobile adverts on clothing, cosmetics, and jewellery. Less than 10% of the participants prefer other mobile adverts. Most of the participants (65%) said they prefer newspapers as a mode of advertising and 35% said they prefer mobile phones. Most of the participants (65%) have once entered a promotion via mobile phone and 35% did not. The same proportion of participants (65%) who have once entered a promotion via mobile phone will enter another one. Most of the participants prefer SMS as a promotion entry method, 23% prefer entry forms, 15% prefer till point, 14% prefer scratch and win, and 11% prefer Facebook and radio call-in. The aim of the research was to determine consumer responsiveness to mobile marketing and the extent to which it has been adopted by marketers. Four key research questions were aimed at narrowing down the subject. They were also

aimed at helping the researcher identify and explain of the issue. The structure of the research questions were as follow:

- Other than making calls and sending text messages, what else do consumers use their mobile phones for?
- How often; if at all do mobile users interact with mobile marketing techniques?
- To what extent are mobile phone users' decisions influenced by mobile marketing techniques?
- What recommendations can be given to marketers regarding acceptable mobile marketing?

Mobile marketing has a place in today's marketing. The findings of this research were consistent with the philosophies presented in the theoretical context. The data collected from the survey was analysed using SPSS software version 21. A Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.510 confirmed the reliability of the research. The research showed that mobile marketing is an important and effective tool for getting adverts and information to consumers because it is a part of every individual's life regardless of age.

5. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Mobile phone usage has increased in Johannesburg over the past decade. There are four mobile networks = MTN, Vodacom, Cell C and Telkom. This research was aimed at determining consumer responsiveness to mobile marketing and the extent to which it has been adopted by marketers. The research study was motivated by personal interest in the use of mobile phones for marketing as mobile phones have become a very popular and most used device catering to the needs of all demographics and age groups. Mobile marketing tends to be a cheaper alternative to advertising when compared to other forms of advertising. This study has not been fully explored in the Johannesburg market and the scope for further studies should be considered. The quantitative research method was used and data collection was done through the use of questionnaires which were circulated to 200 respondents. A trial study was done in Northriding on a small sample. The important conclusion from the research is that mobile marketing is an effective tool for companies which should be focused on for specialised items such as a car, insurance, house, cellphones, mobile networks, electronics, clothing, and cosmetics.

5.1 Conclusions from the primary research

The study was aimed at determining consumer responsiveness to mobile marketing and the extent to which mobile marketing has been adopted by marketers. The research objectives were to outline the different uses of mobile technology by consumers, to determine the incidence with which mobile phone users interact with mobile marketing techniques, to determine the extent to which mobile phone users decisions are influenced by mobile marketing techniques and to make recommendations on the optimal use of mobile marketing. With the use of this study, it was established that, although it might not be the first choice of receiving marketing communications, the majority of the people would still like to receive adverts via their mobile, proving that mobile marketing has a place in marketing. Although emails were highlighted as the most preferred method of receiving marketing communications, it is not clear if these are received via the mobile phone or other gadgets such as desktop computers and laptops. With 34% of the South African population owning mobile phones, it is safe to assume that the internet and email are accessed via mobile phones. Consumers have responded to adverts which focus on travel, accommodation, clothing, cosmetics, jewellery, cellphones, mobile networks, and electronics, and are the adverts which have been most responded to. Mobile marketing efforts should focus on these products. As seen in the findings of this research, adverts are recalled if they are frequent and if they save money. Adverts should focus on saving consumers money.

5.2 Recommendations

Some interesting recommendations can be deduced from the findings of the research regarding mobile marketing methods.

5.2.1 Managerial recommendations

The salient point which is clear in this research is that mobile marketing is an adequate tool of communication which can be used to broadcast marketing information and change the consumers' decision to purchase.

5.2.2 Optimal use of mobile marketing

Traditional mobile phone methods of marketing have gained popularity among South African companies; they have traditionally used SMS and MMS communication as a method to advertise. However, the market is swiftly changing and starting to accept emails, Internet, and social media as advertising platforms. From the findings in this research, 34% of South African mobile phone users have smartphones, this creates a new market for mobile internet, social media and mobile email adverts. It is important that marketers should also use the other methods of marketing communication mix as 28 million people use radio and 26 million people use televisions in South Africa, proving that these gadgets are still important in the consumers' lives and in information sharing. Mobile marketing cannot replace the conventional marketing communication methods completely, but can complement the efforts and create an interactive platform for marketers and their consumers.

5.2.3 Type of product advertised

It is recommended that companies who are in the cellphone, mobile networks, and clothing, cosmetics, jewellery, cars, houses and insurance should adopt mobile marketing techniques as people respond more to adverts containing these products. The findings showed that 81% of the respondents who have responded to adverts with these products. Although all the other products also have a place for mobile marketing, they were not popular amongst the respondents. It is important to take note that today's consumers are cash-strapped and are always looking for ways to save money. Promotions and sale adverts are therefore the most preferred.

5.2.4 Target specific mobile networks

Mobile network providers have an effect on whether its subscribers are willing to receive mobile adverts. This was proven by the hypothesis which showed Cell C and Telkom subscribers like to receive mobile adverts. Telkom and Cell C are associated with people who are looking for affordable high-value items. It is recommended that marketers should direct most of their adverts to Cell C and Telkom subscribers as they are the most receptive. This was shown by the hypothesis results in the research.

5.2.5 Segment adverts by age group and location

With data available from mobile marketing organisations, marketers are able to target their mobile advertising to the right age for their products as well as target a specific area in which the target audience live. This is an advantage over traditional forms of marketing communication which cannot drill down to targeting the age groups.

5.2.6 Use Internet as a form of advertising

From the findings of the research, marketers should use the internet to advertise their products; one of the key uses of mobile phones is the internet. Major websites are now being adjusted to fit on mobile phone screens. With 34% users in South Africa owning smartphones, there is a need to direct some marketing efforts to this segment.

5.3 Limitations

Even with substantial theories and facts drawn from the research findings which could be linked to the population, there are some limitations to this research. Firstly the research was limited to a handful of respondents, two hundred (200) people who are based in Johannesburg versus the total population size of just over ten and a half (10.5) million. The total number of respondents excluded responses from the Johannesburg townships which meant that there was a great degree of bias towards people who stay in urban areas. It is recommended that future research should be conducted with a wider and larger sample size. Secondly, the research focused on the responsiveness of consumers to mobile marketing, but disregarded the mode used to respond. This does not give marketers a full toolset to advertise and get responses. Adverts without a full call to action and clear directions on how to respond will not be effective. Thirdly, the research focused on consumers only, further study should also include marketers and the results they have got from mobile marketing. The time factor and the scope of the research left out many theories and models which were discussed and it generalised many of the theories and models. Future studies should aim to combine quantitative and qualitative research findings in order to build a strong business case. In future to clearly address all research objectives a qualitative research via in-depth interviews may need to be done to get comprehensive data on the topic. Fourthly, the research used non-probability sampling technique yet it was a quantitative study, which is limiting. Further studies should include interviews.

5.4 Future research areas

This study was limited to the area of Johannesburg, future research has a potential to drill down into the different mobile marketing uses with special emphasis on internet and social mobile as marketing communication methods. The study should highlight the likely adverts which are acceptable and the designs of the adverts. It is paramount to consider increasing the size of the sample as 200 respondents might not be enough to make a meaningful recommendation. Mobile marketing and mobile phone service providers should be interviewed to get a view of the actual mobile marketing efforts which have been successful. A study into companies will give a comparison between what companies have experienced and what consumers think as consumers don't always do what they claim.

5.5 Conclusion

From the information contained in this study, it can be observed that mobile marketing is an effective tool for advertising. Information shared via mobile phones can be used to influence a purchase decision. Companies who advertise using mobile phones are able to personalise adverts depending on the location of the targeted market. Mobile advertising can be used by companies who require a cheaper alternative method of communication and those who have had their products or services fail as a second chance for their products. Most of the respondents indicated that they preferred to receive mobile adverts and to enter promotions using their mobile phones.

References

- [1] Kotler, P. and Keller, K.L. (2006). *Marketing management. 12th edition*. New Jersey. Pearson Prentice Hall.
- [2] GSMA (2014). State of the Industry 2013: Mobile financial services for the unbanked. Available: <http://www.gsma.com/mobilefordevelopment/wp->. [Accessed February 1, 2011].
- [3] Leon G. Schiffman, L.G. & Kanuk L. (2009). *Consumer Buyer 5th edition*. New Jersey. Prentice Hall,
- [4] Jobber, D. & Ellis-Chadwick F. (2013). *Principles and practice of marketing*. United Kingdom: McGraw-Hill Education.
- [5] Kristina Heinonen, K. & Strandvik, T. (2005). Communication as an element of service value, *International Journal of Service Industry Management, Vol. 16 Iss: 2*, pp.186 – 198
- [6] Anckar & D’Incau, 2000 Customer relationship management through mobile technologies: exploratory study on Indian Youth. *International Journal of Information Systems and Social Change Volume 3 Issue 4, October 2012* pp 65-83
- [7] Kotler, P. and Keller, K.L. (2009). *Marketing management. 13th Edition*. New Jersey. Pearson Prentice Hall.
- [8] Hutton, J. (2011). *Mobile phones dominate in South Africa*, Mobile Insights Available: <http://www.nielsen.com/us/en/insights/news/2011/mobile-phones-dominate-in-south-africa.html>. [Accessed 13 March 2017]
- [9] Andrews, L. Drennan, J. & Russell-Bennett, R. (2012). Linking perceived value of mobile marketing with the experiential consumption of mobile phones, *European Journal of Marketing, Vol. 46 Iss: 3/4*, 18.
- [10] Berg, B.L. (2001). *Qualitative research methods for the social sciences*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon, 2001.
- [11] Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2007). *Research methods for business students 4th edition*. Edinburgh: Pearson Education Limited.
- [12] Cooper, D.R. and Schindler, P.S. (2007). *Business research methods 9th edition*. McGraw-Hill: New York.
- [13] Shuttleworth, 2008 Shuttleworth, M. (2008). *How to choose between different research methods. Experiment resources*. Available at: <http://www.experiment-resources.com/different-research-methods.html> [Accessed February 1, 2011].
- [14] Shamoo A.E. & Resnik, D.B. (2009). *Responsible conduct of research*. UK: Oxford University Press.